

MUSEUM OF EDUCATION OF THE FEDERAL DISTRICT

A territory of educational memory

Eva Waisros Pereira¹

Maria Paula Vasconcelos Taunay²

ABSTRACT *The Education Museum of the Federal District arises from the need to identify the educational memory of that territory. The initiative, originated through research linked to the Faculty of Education of the University of Brasilia, takes shape within the scope of the State Department of Education of the Federal District, providing the community with a view of its material, immaterial, cultural and symbolic heritage. The first public school in the Federal District, pilot of the political-pedagogical project formulated by educator Anísio Teixeira, will be rebuilt to house the Museum of Education of the Federal District. Returning to the symbolic landmark of Brasilia, a reference center for educational content is forged, supplied by images and reports from teachers, managers and students. In addition to promoting the qualification of current teachers and their educational enjoyment, the service to visitors includes activities and programs, in order to favor links between the school and society in order to recover the utopia of a quality public school.*

KEYWORDS *Education Museum, Anísio Teixeira, educational memory, history of education, Federal District.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Memories of childhood and other stages of life, preserved in the memory of each individual, serve as identity references that differentiate one person from another. These memories, available within the consciousness, can be accessed, whenever necessary, to affirm the roots and compose a continuous present. Significant moments in the course of life, when stored in memory, preserve information, acquired through experiences, intangible points of the present that generate learning. There is no memory without learning, nor is there learning without experiences.

The conception of time has been discussed since the beginning of Western culture. Over time, experiences occur and the experiences that make up the individual's memory emerge. The events and experiences, when studied through memory records, allow the perception of reality in extended time, which includes past, present and future. *Memories represent an inexhaustible content in words. There is no time without a concept of memory; there is no present without a concept of time; there is no reality without memory and without a notion of the present, past and future* (IZQUIERDO, 1988, p.1).

In modern societies, significant experiences built in the school environment become part of the memory of individuals and can represent a long period of life. As school institutions constitute one of the main locus of

¹ *Faculdade de Educação, Universidade de Brasília, Brasil*

² *Museu da Educação do Distrito Federal, Secretaria de Educação do Distrito Federal, Brasília, DF, Brasil*

formation of the subject, replacing the role previously exercised by the family and the community, educational memories gradually expand, filling more space with more intense experiences. As a territory of learning and remarkable events, the school plays a fundamental role in the formation of the subject's identity, be it teacher or student.

II. The city, the museum and the educational memory

The experiences lived at school constitute a cohesive trait in the group's memory, as an expanded limit between the individual and the collective. Called collective memory, this set of experiences is based on continuity, has plural characteristics and formulates the bases of a collective identity. For Halbwachs (2006), collective memories make us have the perception of having experienced exclusive events, which only we have seen, but can be evoked by others in the same group. This is because, as the author states, we are never alone, even when others are not physically present, because we carry them with us in thought. *To confirm or recall a memory, testimonies in the literal sense of the word are not necessary, that is, individuals present in a material and sensitive form* (idem, ibidem, p. 31).

In this context, it is necessary to reflect on how pedagogy can use these memories to better understand the conceptions and practices of the educational process. What repercussions would these studies have on education and society? How useful are memories of the educational past for the current generation? What contributions could they make to education now and in the future? And, finally, what would be the suitable territory for the storage and reflection of the memories of education?

Such questions converge to the idea of establishing the Education Museum of the Federal District as a specialized place to house the educational memories of the Brazilian capital. This Museum, conceived as a space for the presentation and interpretation of social practice, is a living testimony of a culture. Therefore, its primary function is to offer, through actions and services, conditions for pedagogical mediation, so that the visiting public recognizes itself as a member of the community, by sharing experiences and memories and by understanding its heritage. immaterial. *The public appropriates the museological discourse, (re) elaborates it, and then creates and disseminates a new discourse and the process begins again, and this new discourse will be appropriated by others and history repeats itself* (CURY, 2009).

In Brazilian education, historically, there is no recognition of the experiences developed by the subjects or of their educational practices that promote learning and the construction of knowledge. Speaking of the first schools in Brazil refers to the knowledge of a privatized and monopolized knowledge by religious institutions, of Jesuit tradition, which, for a long period, laid the foundations of the education system in the country, progressively expanded with the territorial expansion of the Portuguese domain (AZEVEDO, 1996). The historical documentation of Brazilian education remained linked to religious identity and kept in archives exclusive to these religious institutions.

After centuries of predominance of the Catholic Church, Brazilian education becomes the responsibility of the imperial government, generating disputes between the crown and the church for an education contrary to the predominance of the Catholic faith. The modernizing project of the Marquis of Pombal, for Portugal and overseas colonies, aimed to strengthen the State's participation in the conduct of education.

In Brazil, in 1760, the first competition was held for the admission of royal teachers to replace ecclesiastics, as well as changes were made to curricula and school organizations. However, *in 1765 no public teacher had yet been appointed in Brazil, although the competition had already taken place five years ago* (SAVIANI, 2008, p. 89). These reforms produced the first official documents that support the studies of the history of education in Brazil.

In addition to that institutionalized knowledge, a complex range of narratives arising from experiences lived by citizens, not crystallized in formal documents, which represent the collective consciousness of individuals and groups, generating memories parallel to privatized knowledge. Thus, family memories, local histories and educational memories acquire a prominent place in the construction of the history of education, *providing it with new sources of research that support the need to understand the symbolic framework, codes and practices of that cultural universe specific* (DUARTE, 2002, p. 141).

III. The Education Museum as a research product

Researchers linked to the Faculty of Education of the University of Brasilia have produced academic studies related to public education in the early days of the Federal District, through documentary research and oral history records, which confirm the need to safeguard and disseminate the contents related to the topic.

Thinking about the beginnings of education in the federal capital refers to a period of great achievements by the Brazilian State, based on a developmentalist ideology aimed at modernizing society and the country's means of production. Brasília emerges as a goal synthesis of President Juscelino Kubitschek's political platform, aiming at national integration through its interiorization. The construction of the new capital was an epic and has marked characteristics in the formation of the regional collective memory. Brasília, the capital of Brazil opened in 1960, is distinguished from conventional cities, as an idealized city, with peculiarities expressed in the Report of the Pilot Plan of Brasília, as

a city planned for orderly and efficient work, but at the same time lively and pleasant, proper to reverie and intellectual speculation, capable of becoming, over time, in addition to the center of government and administration, in a focus of culture, most lucid and sensitive in the country (COSTA 1991 p.2).

The city so idealized changed customs of the traditional face of the country, in view of the demand for a native culture that would encourage the valorization of its memories, especially those related to the saga that alludes to its construction. As of 1957, the Brazilian population was unaware of the cultural ties and traditions of the central plateau, an uninhabited region where the pioneer population initially lived.

In the occupied territory, the new Brazilian identity took hold among the farms, paths and paths of the cerrado, where the debate on the construction of the capital would be established as a synthesis of the country's renewed identity (TAUNAY 2015 p.152).

At the city level, architecture proposes to prioritize harmonious coexistence between individuals, creating environments appropriate to modern life and the enhancement of conviviality in the urban environment. In the view of Clarice Lispector, *Brasília is artificial. As artificial as the world should have been when it was created. When the world was created, it was necessary to create a man especially for that world* (LISPECTOR, 1999, p. 40).

What was planned was not only the urban layout, but a process of humanization of its population through a city conceived not as a simple organism capable of satisfactorily and effortlessly fulfilling the vital functions inherent in ANY MODERN CITY, not only as URBS, but as CIVITAS, possessing the attributes inherent to a capital (COSTA 1991, p.3).

The fact of placing man as a priority for modern life in the new capital was also reflected in the education planning of the idealized city. It was up to Anísio Teixeira to propose a new model of education and school to form modern man. The "Plan for School Constructions in Brasília" (TEIXEIRA 1961), a document of

its own, established the offer of a set of schools that would be an example and demonstration for the country's educational system.

As the needs of modern civilization increasingly impose obligations on the school, increasing its attributions and functions, the plan consists - at each level of education, from primary to upper or tertiary, as it is now being called - in a set of buildings, with diverse functions and considerable variety of form and objectives, in order to meet the specific needs of teaching and education and, in addition, to the need for life and social life (idem, ibidem, p.1).

The innovation of the educational model, formulated by the educator Anísio Teixeira, is revealed in the activities proposed for study, work, recreation, administration, decision and interaction, which would transform traditional aspects of education creating spaces for new functions of the school, such as workshops, clubs of sports and recreation, home, commerce, restaurant, museum and theater.

Inspired by the model of the Parque da Bahia School (1950), the educational system in Brasília would function in an integrated manner, ranging from early childhood education to university. Conceived on a pedagogical proposal attentive to the constant transformations of society, the development of its contents was based on the principles of John Dewey's pragmatic philosophy, which advocates the value of experience as a vector of learning.

All living beings act and react in their environment, changing and altering the universe. And man extols this process of interaction and experience. Thanks to language, it makes the experience cumulative and, with the help of its symbolic register, itself the object of the experience. This experience of experience leads you to discover its laws, with which it adds a new dimension to the universe - that of the direction of experience, opening the door to unsuspected developments in the orders and disorders, harmonies and confusions, security and uncertainty of the world, which it constitutes his environment and which he starts to transform for his benefit (TEIXEIRA, 1955, p.1).

Planned as a single education system, accessible to everyone regardless of social class, the proposed school model established an egalitarian basis for the formation of the country's various occupational staff. The educational institutions in Brasília would constitute true educational communities, with their diverse functions and considerable variety of activities, developed full-time. The educational system appears in a revolutionary way compatible with the modernity thought for Brazil then and today. The new city, designed and built for the life of man in modern society brought humanized solutions, less asphalt, less buildings, less masonry and more gardens, spaces for children to play safely.

The "Plano de Construções Escolares de Brasília" (TEIXEIRA, 1961) represents a synthesis of the ideas of educational renewal in Brazil, formulated in the 1920s and 1930s, a period that emerges the movement of intellectuals in favor of the modernization of society and defense of the school public, free and secular. The aforementioned Plan is in line with the ideas expressed in the 1932 Manifesto of Pioneers of Educação Nova, in which Anísio Teixeira is among the signatories, which points to the challenges and priorities present in the developmental, social and economic demands of the time. The climate of enthusiasm of education renovators was driving the creation of associations that put new ideas into circulation.

The awareness was already awakened that, in order to dominate the educational work, in all its extension, it is necessary to have, in a high degree, the habit of attaching, on solid and broad bases, to a set of abstract ideas and general principles, with which we can set up an observation angle, to see clearer and farther and to

unveil, through the tremendous complexity of social problems, broader horizons (MANIFESTO 2010, p. 36).

For more than fifteen years, the research group has been developing studies on the implementation of the education system proposed by Anísio Teixeira for Brasília and its developments. The search for information related to the theme was enriched with an oral history program, in which the protagonists of education - teachers, students and managers -, protagonists of the implementation of the new model of schools, report their experiences as pioneers, one of the most valuable contributions to clarify the memory of education in the Federal District in its beginnings. It is understood that the testimony of these characters is the guarantee of a collection representative of the intentionality that sustained the pedagogical project of public education in the first years of the new capital. On these grounds, the trend in favor of a museological discourse is supported as a necessary reference for the meaning of educational heritage and for the visibility of the evoked memories. According to Tucci Carneiro (2011), *every file is an invention and every narrative is a construction composed of a set of documents selected by a group and / or individual that gives them form and content* (p.328).

The research collection destined to the Education Museum of the Federal District has textual documents, videos, photographs, school furniture, teaching materials, diplomas, whiteboards, pens, literacy primers, textbooks, children's books, reading books, notebooks, abacus, educational games, school folders, lunch boxes, posters, mimeographs, projectors, newsletters, school notebooks and others. The safeguarding of these goods allows the symbolic recomposition of an era, a territory and its culture, as well as the support of innovative and transforming actions necessary for the emancipation of society. The preserved cultural assets, in addition to being an evocation of the past, as a primary source of observation, can mobilize the creative imagination to invent other social practices.

Based on this logic, the cultural assets housed in the Museum should boost the pedagogical imagination of teachers and students in the Federal District and contribute to the development of a critical spirit in the face of the historicity, the contradictions, the discontinuities of educational policies that have followed since the creation of the new capital. Recognizing, collectively, a heritage, strengthens the sense of belonging to the cultural and environmental territory that sustains the community identity.

This memory territory is materialized through the reconstruction of the first public school in the Federal District, called Júlia Kubitschek, and, currently, destined to host the Museum for its symbolic value. Inaugurated on October 18, 1957, the Júlia Kubitschek school served the first students, children of workers and employees of the future capital, even before its foundation, thus being the pilot of the emerging political-pedagogical project. As a laboratory for educational experiences, along the lines proposed by Anísio Teixeira, the school was designed by Oscar Niemeyer and was originally built in Candangolândia, the first housing nucleus in the city that housed the Companhia Urbanizadora da Nova Capital, NOVACAP, the company responsible for the construction of Brasília.

The reconstruction of this school in the same place where it was initially built and sadly not preserved aims to recover, through research, objects, documents and testimonies from the educators and students of that time to reinvent the imagination of the Brazilian capital. In this way, the symbolic gesture of signaling to the whole country the inventive possibilities of the Brazilian people and an educational project aimed at the effective growth of the individual and society is repeated.

The Museum, as well as the Júlia Kubitschek school in its original design, are wooden constructions, according to the environment of the camps prevalent in the early days of the city. Its construction in the Parque Vivencial e Ecológico dos Pioneiros, in Candangolândia, projects an architecture based on compliance with the principles of sustainability. Due to its characteristics, it comes close to the purposes of an ecomuseum, a contemporary model of a museum in which the purpose of preserving and exposing samples for communication, instruction, memory, leisure, research and tourist attraction through the specific use of collections is implicit.

ecological. In this sense, as a territory for reflection of collective memories and a place of reverie, it will set educators and students apart from the exhibition rooms.

This configuration became explicit with the recent planting of 2,400 seedlings of native species, which gave rise to the “Jardim do Cerrado”, symbolizing the cornerstone of the Education Museum of the Federal District. In this garden, ecological and sensory trails integrate a route designed for the building's surroundings, where the planting of permacultural gardens, agroforestry and senses forests, with ornamental and aromatic species, is proposed, which aim to enhance the place through the observation of the nature.

Thus, outside the Museum, students, teachers, other segments of the community and other visitors will be able to enjoy spaces designed for contemplation, reflection and leisure. The construction of a mini-city is also foreseen, composed of houses in the style of wooden constructions from the beginning of Brasília, to install art-education workshops, manual and technical occupations and bodily and scenic activities, inspired by pragmatic orientation. Anísio Teixeira's educational plan for schools in Brasília. The external area will also have a Geodesic Module, with capacity for one hundred and twenty people, and the “Parque das In Invenções”, designed as a favorable place to create opportunities for socialization, experimentation and learning through games.

In this way, the ambience designed for the museum may favor the spectrum of recalling educational situations, both as a student and as a teacher. It is understood that, through the alternation between knowledge and remembrance, this visitor will be able to access the memories of his school education, in order to contribute to the development of his identity and his place of belonging in society.

IV. The museum, the mission and the programs

Unlike many museums that have their headquarters previously built, only then to adapt their spaces to the needs of the exhibition content, the Museum of Education of the Federal District had its architectural project conceived from definitions contained in its museum plan. The importance of this arrangement is to enable the use of the institution's spaces in the manner planned to meet the demands present in its mission and in its programs.

The mission of the Museum of Education is to preserve, safeguard and disseminate the memory of public education in the Federal District, with a view to strengthening the identity of the school and the teacher, as well as contributing to the quality and renewal of educational processes, for the benefit of the city and brasiliense education. In this sense, museum and education complement each other as they promote the development of a collective awareness of the history of local education. The treatment of the contents of educational memories converges in these spheres, gradually expanding with the dissemination of the collection and, especially, through educational actions carried out with different audiences, characterizing the Education Museum of the Federal District as a space for reflection and debate.

The user audience is thus configured as the main objective of the Museum of Education of the Federal District, in accordance with the new parallels of museology that emerge at the General Conference of Museums, in Paris (1971). Thus, it performs its function in opposition to traditional museology, which values the collection itself and manages it independently of its social use. In this context, it exerts a critical and transforming role in projecting itself as an integral museum and transitioning to a social museology, open to society and the real world as a political banner.

The new museology must come from the public, that is, from two types of users, society and the individual. Instead of being at the service of objects, the museum should be at the service of men. Instead of the museum "of something", the museum

"for something": for education, identification, confrontation, awareness, in short, museum for a community, function of that same community (COELHO, 1999 p.45) .

In order to exercise the functions of a museum for the community, several specialized care programs in educational sectors were designed at the museum level to make the links between school and society more effective.

The educational program of the Museum of Education establishes as a priority the continuing education for teachers in the Federal District, in partnership with the University of Brasília. The access to the educational memories of their predecessors brings teachers of today closer to the pedagogical proposals and innovative methodologies used to overcome problems and solutions present in the school routine in the beginning of the city, stimulating creative changes in today's education. In addition, these activities strengthen the teacher's sense of belonging and their recognition as the protagonist of current history.

It should also be mentioned that the educational program organizes different itineraries, suitable for different audiences, including teachers and students from the public school system, the community of the Federal District, in particular, that of Candangolândia and tourists in transit. In relation to students, the routes are directed to the interests of each segment, seeking flexible, creative and playful forms, according to the age group of each group. Considering the processes of socialization and psychogenetic development, the planned activities aim to stimulate curiosity, create a sense of collectivity and perceive education as a participatory process, capable of reflecting on their attitudes. For this, the museum will have a multidisciplinary team of professors from areas such as Arts, History, Biology, Letters, Museology and others, responsible for educational actions and contents.

The school going to the Museum can understand the role of preserving culture and objects. Interpreting the relationship between man and the environment, the influence of cultural heritage, the identity of individuals and social groups, the school grows within museums through actions aimed at better understanding, transformation and social development. (SANTOS, 2008 p. 141)

Accessibility is ensured to all visitors, in accordance with the provisions of the educational program, such as assistance to people with special needs. Based on their specificity - sensory, physical and / or mental - we will seek to insert and develop the potential of each of the segments, in order to foster the integration relations with the Museum. Your contact with the exhibition pieces will take place through your own sensory paths, using audio description resources, through direct contact with some pieces reproduced in two-dimensional or three-dimensional forms or through adapted games and communication through the system of pounds.

For the development of museum activities, the educational program interacts with the other programs established in the museum's structure. The following programs should be mentioned: institutional, exhibitions, collections, research and extension, exchange, promotion and funding, communication and cultural diffusion, people management and security.

The exhibition program defines three types of exhibitions: long-term, short-term and itinerant. Upon entering the museum, the visitor will be welcomed and will receive guidance from guides in the exhibition rooms and on the ecological trails. In order to raise public awareness, the visitation route will start in a cinema room projected at 180 degrees, to watch a film that will contextualize the period of the construction of Brasília and installation of the public education system in the Federal District.

The former classrooms of the Júlia Kubitschek School, with necessary adaptations to meet the demands contained in the museological and museographic plans, will host the long-term exhibition.

In this pedagogical environment, they will be presented in various material supports and electronic media, textual documents, photographs and audiovisuals related to the educational proposals and methodologies adopted in the early days of the city. The long-term exhibition constitutes the guiding thread of the expographic project, which illustrates the pioneering spirit, the inventiveness of the Brasília community and the utopias that preceded and fulfilled the dream of the new capital.

The short-term exhibitions, composed of samples produced by the museum staff or by segments of the educational community, as well as by local artists or interested researchers, will present productions related to education in the Federal District. The traveling exhibitions are also an extension of the museum's exhibition programs and are intended for public schools and other spaces in the city, with a view to spreading the memory of education in the Federal District and exposing the museum's heritage.

V. CONCLUSION

Territory of memory, education and research

The Education Museum of the Federal District is established as a reference center for educational content that favors the qualification of current teachers and their enjoyment, also promoting itself as an institution capable of mapping impressions of the visiting public around the exposed content and creating a sensitive field of observation to perceive education as a humanization process.

The expectation is that the brasiliense, when visiting the museum, recognizes his educational past, with a reflective look that illuminates his conscience, pointing out the influences of school formation in his identity. It is expected that the visitor, when in contact with the material, immaterial, cultural and symbolic heritage exposed in the museum, will reach an understanding of his belonging to his historical time.

Being a place of memory, education and research, it is intended that this museum plays a transforming role in society, based on the understanding of the relationship between the past and the present and the possibilities that illuminate the future. The promotion of historical research on education in the Federal District will broaden the look on the theme, offering new elements capable of supporting transforming proposals for contemporary education. Revisiting yesterday's school to invent tomorrow's school is the motto that guides the intentionality of the educational actions developed in the nascent institution, in its museum field.

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